

Editorial

Inaugural Issue of the Journal of Economics, Law, and Society (JELS)

It is with great pleasure that we present the first issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*, a peer-reviewed journal which aims to foster academic discourse on the interconnections between economics, law, and society. It is with great expectations and enthusiasm that we begin this journal from Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) and confident that this journal will be of immense benefits to the academia especially in the newly emerging area of Islamic finance.

The formation of JELS is more so due to the realization of the importance of the multidisciplinary approach to solving tasks that require synthesis and integration of theory and practice across disciplines. In the modern integrated global environment, the interactions between economic processes, legal regulation and social phenomena become even more significant. Our goal is to encourage high-quality scholarship, critical thinking, and meaningful discourse on these critical issues while promoting academic study and intellectual exchange.

JELS aims at ensuring quick dissemination of research findings between researchers, universities, as well as other academic institutions across the world. Our journal will focus on the advancement that is current within various fields of study like business and management law, public administration, sociology/anthropology, economics, social work/social policy, history, education/teaching, psychology, political science/government, ethics/moral philosophy, and many others. Thus, we intend to have a broad focus in order to provide readers with the theoretical and empirical materials of an interdisciplinary nature that integrate legal and economic approaches.

All manuscripts sent to JELS are subject to rigorous double-blind review to ensure that publications in our journal reflect the highest standards of scholarship. Recently we have been focusing on new and developing topics, Islamic finance in particular, based on our conviction that more innovative solutions to the problems of financial intermediation should be sought.

The editorial board for JELS consists of distinguished academics and practitioners from various fields of law and economics. Thanks to their experience and commitment, authors will receive constructive feedback to improve their work while the review process remains effective and fast. That is why we are pleased to present to readers the rich variety of materials reflecting law and economics thinking with representatives from different countries.

As we enter this new course of action, it is our intention to become increasingly well-known on

the international level. Turning to the focus and scope of JELS, this journal sets out to solicit papers that are originated from and discuss various legal systems and theoretical inter-cultural topics. We will continue to encourage submissions of articles that contribute to improved methods in the vast area of Islamic economics, Islamic business and management, Islamic finance, and Islamic banking studies. It is also important to note that our target audience mainly consists of academicians, college teachers, postgraduate students, and other practitioners, ensuring that our journal serves as a valuable resource for those engaged in the field.

JELS has the support of the *Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)*, and it is our intention to make this journal one of the leading academic journals not only in BiH but also throughout the world. In the future, we will try our best to ensure JELS will be included in top databases that could help to improve its visibility and significance among the academia.

We encourage you to join us in the exploration of the actual link which exists between economics, law and society through the first issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*. We hope to continue receiving your stimulating inputs and to help build up the academic community via this journal. Thank you for being part of this journey and indeed, we do hope that you will be both informed and inspired by the research and information contained in these pages.

Continuing the strong focus on economic development, this inaugural issue features a variety of insightful studies. Smolo's analysis challenges conventional wisdom by demonstrating a complex relationship between finance, institutions, and economic growth (pp. 5-22). His findings suggest the need for nuanced approaches based on specific contexts.

Shifting the focus to consumer behavior, Knezović et al. explore green purchase intentions in the Middle East (pp. 23-38). Their research finds that factors like age, gender, and education have minimal impact, while geographic location holds some influence. This research highlights the need to explore green consumer behavior in the region further.

Mešković et al. delve into the under-utilized potential of Islamic investment deposits in Bosnia and Herzegovina (pp. 39-53). Their study reveals a significant knowledge gap among depositors, hindering wider adoption. The authors emphasize the need for education and awareness campaigns to unlock the potential of these deposits for financial inclusion.

The growing importance of sustainable finance is explored by Ibrić et al. who analyze the global green bond market (pp. 55-71). Their research highlights Europe's leadership in issuance, with Bosnia and Herzegovina making its debut in 2023. The study underscores the need to address limitations like inadequate infrastructure to enable further development of the green bond market in the region.

Rounding out the issue, Metadžer et al. investigate the role of sukuk, a Shari'ah-compliant financial instrument, in portfolio diversification (pp. 73-89). Their study, focusing on the Dubai market, reveals a dynamic relationship between sukuk and conventional stock market, but concludes that sukuk may not function as a traditional safe-haven asset.

Our journal's inaugural issue presents a rich research tapestry, offering valuable insights for academics, policymakers, and practitioners alike. We look forward to continuing this exploration of critical themes in future issues.

Finally, we express our profound thanks to all the authors, reviewers, and other members of the editorial board for their significant contributions that has led to the production of this first issue. It is my pleasure to extend my sincere appreciation to you for your impressive and tremendous efforts

that created such a solid basis for JELS and paving the way for the coming issues loaded with remarkable research papers and remarkable dialogue. We eagerly anticipate starting the new journey and genuinely appreciate your support and input as we aim to develop JELS into an influential journal in the areas of economics, law, and society. Greetings to everyone visiting JELS, where advancing interdisciplinary research frontiers is our mission.

Edib Smolo

Editor-in-Chief

Journal of Economics, Law & Society (JELS)

